

INVESTIGATION OF CARDIOPULMONARY CAPACITY, RESPIRATORY FUNCTIONS, DYSPNEA, PHYSICAL ACTIVITY, COGNITION, AND QUALITY OF LIFE OF COVID-19 VACCINATED INDIVIDUALS: PRELIMINARY REPORT

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ABSTRACT

This study compared CoronaVac-vaccinated individuals with BNT162b2-vaccinated individuals regarding cardiopulmonary capacity, pulmonary functions, dyspnea, physical activity, cognition, and quality of life. This observational report had a comparative and cross-sectional design. Thirteen individuals with BNT162b2 vaccination and seven with CoronaVac vaccination participated in the study. People aged 18-65 years who had received only two doses of one type of vaccine were included in the study. Cardiopulmonary capacity, respiratory functions, dyspnea, physical activity, and cognition were evaluated using a 6-minute walk test, spirometry, the London Chest Activity of Daily Living Scale, the International Physical Activity Questionnaire-Long Form, and the Montreal Cognitive Assessment, respectively. As sub-fields of health-related quality of life, physical functioning, pain, role limitations due to physical health, role limitations due to emotional problems, emotional well-being, social functioning, energy/fatigue, and general health were assessed using the Short Form-36. There were some significant differences between groups in pain ($t = 2.60$, $p = .018$, $d = 1.22$), emotional well-being ($t = 2.34$, $p = .031$, $d = 1.10$), and social functioning ($U = 18.0$, $p = .026$, $rrb = .604$). Cardiopulmonary capacity, respiratory functions, dyspnea, physical activity, cognition, and other sub-fields of health-related quality of life were not significantly different between groups ($p > .05$). CoronaVac-vaccinated individuals showed better results in pain, emotional well-being, and social functioning. However, future studies with a larger sample size are needed. This study was granted by the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye (1919B012303064).

Keywords: COVID-19 Vaccines, Cardiorespiratory Fitness, Spirometry, Dyspnea, Sedentary Behavior, Cognition, Quality of Life

INTRODUCTION

On December 31, 2019, pneumonia with unknown etiology emerged in Wuhan, China. The World Health Organization announced that these cases were caused by a new coronavirus and characterized this new virus as a respiratory disease. In 2020, the pandemic caused by the virus COVID-19 caused outbreaks around the world.

COVID-19, a virus that affects the respiratory tract and lungs, has had a severe impact worldwide as one of the most significant health crises in history. Therefore, COVID-19-related structures are crucial for human health and social life. This disease, which is transmitted by droplets from the upper respiratory tract, is easily transmitted when other people come into contact with the droplets released by sneezing or coughing infected people with their hands and touching their mouth, nose, or eyes without cleaning their hands (Kutlu et al., 2021). To contain the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic, educational institutions worldwide have been temporarily closed, travel restrictions have been imposed, social isolation has been ensured, and quarantine rules such as staying at home unless necessary have been implemented. Despite all measures taken worldwide, the COVID-19 pandemic spread with new mutations and variants. The only way for our immune system to recognize a pathogen and produce specific immune defenses against it is to encounter the pathogen, which can be done either with weakened pathogens or non-infectious parts of the pathogen through vaccination or with the pathogen itself. A vaccine is the introduction into the body of weakened, neutralized forms, parts, or toxins of infectious disease-causing pathogens that do not cause disease. In this way, our cells recognize pathogens when they are harmless and produce specific antibodies against them. Hence, when confronted with the pathogen, it uses its antibodies to eliminate the microbes before they can produce disease.

Two vaccines against COVID-19, BNT162b2 and CoronaVac, are widely used worldwide. Although there have been many studies on the efficacy and side effects of these vaccines, how both vaccines perform in different circumstances is still under investigation. These approved urgent-use vaccines have been introduced in many countries since late 2020. Although precautions are often taken, the rapid spread of influenza-like viruses, the inadequate production of vaccines, and, most importantly, the weak healthcare systems in countries where the disease persists cause these pandemics to continue (Uzun & Ulutaşdemir, 2020). To the authors' knowledge, investigations in the literature on the systemic effects of the COVID-19 virus and vaccines developed to combat it have not provided significant information on respiratory functions, cardiopulmonary capacity, and physical activity levels. However, further studies on the quality of life and dyspnea in vaccinated individuals are needed in the literature. This study not only uniquely demonstrates the effects of these two vaccine types on the relevant variables but also compares them with each other. This study addresses some of the physical and mental effects of vaccines on vaccinated individuals. This study took a comprehensive approach, not limiting the effects of COVID-19 vaccines to pulmonary capacity alone but also including various domains such as cognitive function, quality of life, respiratory function, cardiopulmonary capacity, and physical activity. This has allowed us to assess the effects of the vaccine on individuals' overall health status and quality of life.

This study compared CoronaVac-vaccinated individuals with BNT162b2-vaccinated individuals regarding cardiopulmonary capacity, respiratory functions, dyspnea, physical activity, cognition, and quality of life. It was hypothesized that inactivated CoronaVac vaccinated individuals' cardiopulmonary capacity, respiratory functions, dyspnea, physical activity, cognition, or quality of life is different from that of BNT162b2 mRNA vaccinated individuals. Therefore, the research question of this study is: Do inactivated CoronaVac-vaccinated individuals have a different cardiopulmonary capacity, respiratory functions, dyspnea, physical activity, cognition, or quality of life than BNT162b2 mRNA-vaccinated individuals?

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Design and participants

This observational report had a comparative and cross-sectional design. The study followed the Declaration of Helsinki on Medical Protocol and Ethics. The Clinical Research Ethics Committee of Kastamonu University approved this study (Decision number: 2023-KAEK-123). It was conducted at the Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation Centre for Research and Training of Karabük University. People aged 18-65 years who had received only two doses of one type of vaccine were included in the study. The exclusion criteria for participants are the following: (1) diagnosis of COVID-19 in the last 1 year, (2) pregnancy and breastfeeding, (3) cardiopulmonary, neuromuscular, musculoskeletal, psychiatric, mental, metabolic, rheumatic, and malignant diseases that may affect measurements, (4) medication, exercise therapy or physiotherapy within the last 1 month that may affect measurements, and (5) general anesthesia, surgery, or intensive care in the last 6 months. Participant patients gave informed consent before inclusion.

Outcome measures

Cardiopulmonary capacity, respiratory functions, dyspnea, physical activity, and cognition were evaluated using a 6-minute walk test ("ATS statement: guidelines for the six-minute walk test," 2002), spirometry (Miller et al., 2005), the London Chest Activity of Daily Living Scale (Saka et al., 2020), the International Physical Activity Questionnaire-Long Form (Saglam et al., 2010), and the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (Selekler et al., 2010), respectively. As sub-fields of health-related quality of life, physical functioning, pain, role limitations due to physical health, role limitations due to emotional problems, emotional well-being, social functioning, energy/fatigue, and general health were assessed using the Short Form-36 (Demiral et al., 2006).

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using Jamovi Version 2.3.28 (The Jamovi Project, Sydney, Australia). The statistical significance level was accepted as $p < .05$. The assumption of normal distribution was evaluated by the Shapiro-Wilk test. An independent sample t-test or Mann-Whitney U test was used to compare numerical variables between groups. Cohen's d or rank biserial correlation was used for effect sizes at independent sample t-test or Mann Whitney U test, respectively.

FINDINGS

Thirteen individuals with BNT162b2 vaccination and seven with CoronaVac vaccination participated in the study. Age, height, weight, body mass index, education, marital status, smoking, and alcohol consumption showed no difference between groups ($p > .05$). However, the female sex percentage was significantly higher in BNT162b2 mRNA vaccinated participants.

There were significant differences between groups in pain ($t = 2.60, p = .018$), emotional well-being ($t = 2.34, p = .031$), and social functioning ($U = 18.0, p = .026$). Cardiopulmonary capacity, respiratory functions, dyspnea, physical activity, cognition, and other health-related quality of life sub-fields were not significantly different between groups ($p > .05$).

Table 1. Results of between-group analysis

Outcome measures	Statistics	<i>p</i>	<i>ES</i>
Cardiopulmonary capacity			
<i>Distance in 6-minute walk test</i>	<i>t</i> _{Welch} = 1.79	.112	.908
Respiratory functions (spirometry)			
<i>Forced vital capacity</i>	<i>t</i> _{Welch} = 1.66	.138	.847
<i>Forced expiratory volume in the first second</i>	<i>t</i> _{Welch} = .582	.576	.292
<i>Ratio of forced expiratory volume in the first second to forced vital capacity</i>	<i>U</i> = 35.0	.427	.231
<i>Peak expiratory flow</i>	<i>t</i> _{Student} = .246	.809	.115
<i>Forced expiratory flow at 25%</i>	<i>t</i> _{Student} = .175	.863	.082
<i>Forced expiratory flow at 75%</i>	<i>t</i> _{Student} = 1.22	.237	.573
<i>Mean forced expiratory flow (25% to 75%)</i>	<i>t</i> _{Student} = .558	.584	.262
Dyspnea during activities of daily living			
<i>London Chest Activity of Daily Living Scale</i>	<i>U</i> = 30.5	.243	.330
Physical activity			
International Physical Activity Questionnaire – Long Form	<i>U</i> = 42.0	.817	.077
Cognition			
Montreal Cognitive Assessment	<i>U</i> = 27.5	.162	.396
Health-related quality of life (Short form-36)			
<i>Physical functioning</i>	<i>U</i> = 26.0	.118	.429
<i>Pain</i>	<i>t</i> _{Student} = 2.60	.018*	1.22
<i>Role limitations due to physical health</i>	<i>U</i> = 28.5	.124	.374
<i>Role limitations due to emotional problems</i>	<i>U</i> = 36.5	.485	.198
<i>Emotional well-being</i>	<i>t</i> _{Student} = 2.34	.031*	1.10
<i>Social functioning</i>	<i>U</i> = 18.0	.026*	.604
<i>Energy/fatigue</i>	<i>t</i> _{Student} = 1.61	.125	.754
<i>General health</i>	<i>t</i> _{Student} = 1.18	.253	.553

SD: Standard deviation / *min*; *max*: minimum; maximum / *U*: Mann Whitney *U* test / *t*_{Student}: Student's *t*-test / *t*_{Welch}: Welch's *t*-test / *ES*: Effect size / *: *p* < .05.

DISCUSSION

The present study compared inactivated CoronaVac-vaccinated individuals with mRNA BNT162b2-vaccinated individuals regarding cardiopulmonary capacity, respiratory functions, dyspnea, physical activity, cognition, and quality of life. CoronaVac-vaccinated individuals showed better pain, emotional well-being, and social functioning results than mRNA BNT162b2-vaccinated individuals. Cardiopulmonary capacity, respiratory functions, dyspnea, physical activity, and cognition demonstrated no significant difference. Six months after acute infection, COVID-19 survivors mainly had fatigue, muscle weakness, sleep difficulties, anxiety, or depression (Huang et al., 2023). The most common symptoms in COVID-19 survivors after 6 months were fatigue, post-exertional malaise, and cognitive dysfunction (Davis et al., 2021). Respiratory function, functional capacity, quality of life, and fatigue in individuals with severe COVID-19 infection were impaired even 6 months after intensive care unit discharge (Sirayder et al., 2022). Some studies in the literature examine the association between COVID-19 vaccination and physical activity (Nieman, 2021). Initial results from BNT162b2 mRNA vaccine trials showed similar efficacy between individuals with and without obesity (low physical activity) (Townsend et al., 2021).

In addition, the most common systemic side effects of CoronaVac vaccines include fatigue, drowsiness, muscle pain, joint pain, and cough (Dadras et al., 2022). Numbness in the extremities, chest pain, palpitations, and hypertension have been reported as other systemic adverse events in CoronaVac-vaccinated individuals, although not vaccine-related (SeyedAlinaghi et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2021). The results of the present study can only be extrapolated to some due to low sample size.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Health-related quality of life was only significantly improved in inactivated CoronaVac-vaccinated individuals compared to mRNA BNT162b2-vaccinated individuals. However, future studies with a larger sample size are needed.

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